

ALIGNED SHORT FIBRE COMPOSITES WITH HIGH PERFORMANCE

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1 Introduction

Discontinuous fibre composites can achieve high structural performance when the fibre aspect ratio is sufficiently high to enable load transfer and high levels of alignment are obtained [1,2]. Furthermore, it is widely recognized that aligned short fibre composites allow considerable deformation during moulding, e.g.[3]. In the past, these aligned discontinuous fibre materials have been used for the manufacture of components with complex geometries. However, the studies of aligned discontinuous fibre composites and their manufacturing methods are becoming interesting topics for the development of composite materials with ductile response and the approach taken to the use of recycled composites.

Continuous fibre reinforced composites have high performance for structural applications but tend to fail in a brittle manner, unlike metal. However, aligned discontinuous fibre composites can offer the scope to create a ductile or pseudo-ductile response by deformation and slip at the discontinuities. Okabe and Sasayama[4,5] modelled an aligned discontinuous carbon fibre/polypropylene composite with a Shear-Lag Model and investigated the effect of fibre length on the stress-strain curves, which showed ductility with a reasonable modulus and strength when the fibre length was around the critical fibre length (typically 0.5~1 mm)[1,2]. Despite numerous analytical studies, there have been limited experimental results to validate the model as the required fibre length around the critical length leads to difficulties in producing high-quality specimens with consistent fibre length, good alignment, controlled volume fraction and uniformly distributed fibres[6].

If the fibre aspect ratio is sufficient to support load transfer, experimental work demonstrates that high structural performance can be achieved. According to the manufacturer's data from Hexcel (SBCF: Stretched Broken Carbon Fibre)[7], Pepin Associates (DiscoTex®)[8], Schappe Techniques[9] and the paper from Harper[10], aligned short fibre composites have stiffness and strength retention values of 77-94% and 37-90% compared to continuous unidirectional materials. Generally, they provide discontinuous fibre yarns or prepregs with discontinuous fibres with the length in the range of approximately 10~100 mm. However, as all the materials are made by cutting pre-existing tows, their manufacturing processes cannot be applied to recycle cured composite products. The recycled fibres are generally short (typically below 1 mm) with a random orientation. These fibres can be milled and used as a low-grade additive for nonstructural applications, such as for anti-static and electromagnetic interference shielding as well as for enhanced heat conduction. However, in order to maximize economic and functional viability, recycled fibres should be reused as reinforcement for high performance structural components. The fibre alignment level is a key factor in increasing the fibre volume packing ability, which leads to a high performance for recycled composites[11].

The issue is therefore how to manufacture highly aligned discontinuous preforms directly from short fibres rather than from pre-existing tows in order to offer scope for ductility of composites and closed loop recycling of the fibres. The manufacturing method should be applicable for different fibre types with a fast and continuous process.

Work at University of Bristol has recently shown a new method having a unique fibre orientation

mechanism[12]. The intention of this paper is to introduce the new fibre orientation mechanism and the development process of the new method based on the comparative analysis of conventional fibre alignment methods. This paper also reports some preliminary material test results of specimens obtained from the new short fibre alignment method.

2 Review of conventional discontinuous fibre alignment methods

Characteristics and drawbacks of different manufacturing methods for aligned discontinuous fibre composites directly from short fibres are summarised in Table 1.

In general, although electric (or magnetic) field induced methods can achieve high productivity by dealing with dry fibres with powder type binder, they have their limits in increasing fibre alignment levels [13,14]. As another approach for dry alignment of discontinuous fibres, Ericson et al. [15] manufactured oriented preformed GMT (glass-mat-reinforced thermoplastics) using pneumatic force. The process enabled the fibre/powder mixture to

collide against an orientation plate at high speed before it was sucked towards a perforated steel plate. The geometry of the orientation plates, surface friction of the flow channel and flow factors forced the fibre bundles to orientate transversely to the air flow direction. However, the alignment potential of this method is low, with the majority of fibres oriented between $\pm 52^\circ$.

The converging flow method with a rotating vacuum drum achieved some success with high fibre alignment level with 60% of fibres in the range of $\pm 3^\circ$ using up to 6 mm long fibres[16]. The method consists of 3 major steps: dispersing fibres, aligning fibres, and removing the carrier from the fibre suspension. Fibres are typically suspended in a highly viscous liquid such as glycerine and alignment is achieved by accelerating the carrier liquid through a converging nozzle or channel, forcing the fibres to follow the fluid streamlines. However, the high viscosity of the liquid was shown to be a main factor in decreasing the productivity[17-23].

Table 1 Summary of conventional discontinuous fibre alignment methods

Characteristics		Drawbacks
Electric field induced [13,14]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Handling dry fibres • Fibre length (2-6 mm) • Continuous process 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High electric field intensity • Limitation to fibre types • Low orientation level (70% fibres between $\pm 20^\circ$, 80~90% between $\pm 30^\circ$)
Air flow + mechanically oriented [15]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Handling dry fibres • Fibre length (25 mm) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low volume fraction (~18%) • Low orientation level (the majority of fibers oriented between $\pm 52^\circ$) • Not suitable for short fibres (below 10 mm) • Not continuous process (product type: A sheet)
Converging flow (wet) + suction filter types [3,6,16-23]	Suction: Wire filter mesh (ERDE)[17, 19-23] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fibre orientation direction=Flow stream direction • High viscous-medium (at least 100 cps, glycerine) • Fibre length (~6 mm) • Fibre orientation level (90% fibre between $\pm 15^\circ$) • Continuous process 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low flow rate (Low productivity)
	Suction: Centrifugal force (Rotating vacuum drum filter) [3,6,16,18] <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Orientation level (60% fibre between $\pm 3^\circ$) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not continuous process (product type: A sheet)
Paper making process for aligning fibres [11,24]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fibre orientation direction=Flow stream direction • Low viscous-medium (equal to or greater than 1.5 cps) • Fibre length (10~60 mm) • Continuous process 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low orientation level (unknown) • Not suitable for short fibres (below 10 mm)

Fig.1. Comparison of the fibre orientation mechanism; (a) Paper making process, (b) the 1st design and (c) the 2nd design for manufacturing a tow type aligned preform.

For high productivity, the paper making process uses water with relatively low viscosity in dispersing and aligning the fibres in the direction of the flow. A quantitative level of fibre alignment has not been presented, but experimental results, showing a tensile strength retention of 20% compared to continuous composites [11,24], indicate that it has poor fibre alignment performance, especially for short fibres below 10 mm, although it enables reasonably high fibre volume fraction (~45%). These limitations of conventional flow-induced discontinuous fibre alignment methods and modified paper making processes were previously investigated with Axiomatic Design theory by the authors[12].

3 New developed short fibre alignment method

3.1 Concept of orientation head design for a tow type preform

To sum up, the requirements of a novel short fibre alignment method for the development of a new material and composite recycling are as follows,

- Using randomly oriented short fibres which are not from cutting pre-existing tows.
- Fast and continuous process

- High fibre alignment level
- Applicable fibre length range of from 0.5 to 5 mm

In order to achieve all of the above criteria, the first concept of the orientation device was developed by the authors as shown in Figure 1 (b)[12]. In this new process, when the low viscous fibre suspension flows down an inclined plate, rigid fibres in the suspension collide against the other inclined plate. Then their orientations are changed if the distance between two inclined plates, l , is less than the fibre length while the suspension (low viscous-medium: water) is removed rapidly. Figure 1 (a) clearly shows how the fibre orientation mechanism of the new method differs from the conventional method using water as a suspending fluid (paper making process). However, in the previous research using the first concept, fibre flocculation was observed at the tip of the orientation head due to the low velocity of fluid film flowing down the inclined plate. The orientation head had two functional requirements, changing the fibre orientation and controlling the flow rate and velocity, but only one design parameter, the angle of the orientation plates. Based on the Axiomatic Design theory, it turned out to be a coupled design as shown in Figure 2. Flow retention

Fig. 2. Design development from the 1st concept to the 2nd concept.

therefore occurred at the tip of the orientation head causing fibre misalignment and flocculation. In order to overcome this problem, a fibre suspension jet system was employed for the control of flow rate and velocity. Finally, the 2nd design concept enabled the production of a short fibre aligned preform of thin single tow type illustrated in Figure 1 (c)[12].

3.2 The potential for a tape type preform by improving orientation head design

The orientation head was redesigned to enable a continuous production of a tape-like discontinuous fibre preform in order to increase productivity. As shown in Figure 3 (a), the orientation head in the previous concept had an inclined plate to change the momentum of the fibre suspension and a second plate used as a guide to prevent an overflow that would cause misaligned fibres. This fibre orientation mechanism can be therefore replicated and simplified with two parallel plates; the second plate

has lower height so that the fibre suspension jet can be directed onto the first plate over the second plate as shown in Figure 3(b).

This simplified concept can be extended into a 3D system. A new orientation head design in 3D consists of two parallel plates staggered with a gap l between them which is controllable. As shown in Figure 4, the fibre suspension jet from the nozzle is inclined downwards from the horizontal and oriented at an oblique angle (θ) to the x-z plane to ensure the jet is fully captured within the channel. It is referred to as a single unit of the orientation head. The big advantage of this concept is the ability to extend the orientation head size along the direction perpendicular to the channel; it can allow the manufacture of a wide tape type preform rather than a thin tow preform. For instance, when the orientation head is comprised of two units, two fibre suspension jets hit each orientation plate and then the fibres are aligned and move along each channel between two plates. Subsequently, each tow type

Fig. 3. Fibre orientation mechanism with (a) two inclined plates, (b) two parallel plates.

Fig. 4. Single unit of orientation head.

preform coming from the gaps merges into one narrow tape preform.

4 Experimental methodology

4.1 Discontinuous fibre alignment device

This method is comprised of the following steps:

- a) dispersing the fibres in a liquid dispersion medium (water),
- b) accelerating the dispersion medium through a nozzle to partially align the fibres,
- c) shooting the fibre suspension jet onto the orientation plate and aligning the fibres transversely to the suspension jet,
- d) removing the liquid medium by a suction plate through the moving perforated belt to maintain the fibre orientation,
- e) drying the aligned fibre preform before resin impregnation.

A device for the concept validation of the new design was built to include all of the above steps. The orientation head had two units to make two thin tows for one narrow tape type preform.

4.2 Materials and fabrication

The carbon fibres used are 1.820 g/cm³, 3 mm, and 7 μm in density, length and diameter, respectively. The fibres are sized with a water-soluble polymer of 3.8% (volume fraction) and were supplied from Toho Tenax GmbH. Tensile stiffness and strength of the carbon fibres are 225 GPa and 4344 MPa, respectively.

The suspending fluid is tap water whose density is 0.99 g/cm³ at a temperature of 25°C. The dynamic viscosity of the water is 0.001 kg/ms. An epoxy resin film (1.23 g/cm³, MTM49-3, ACG, UK) was used to impregnate the aligned fibre preforms.

The gap *l* between the parallel plates was 0.7 mm, but the width of preform decreased to 0.5 mm because the surface tension of the water remaining in the preform before it was dried, forced the bundle of fibres to gather at the point where the preform was transferred between the fibre aligning device and the drying device.

Composite samples with different fibre volume fractions were prepared. An areal density of the aligned preform could be controlled by adjusting the process variables. The equation to predict the areal

density (*D_a*) of the preform can be simply written as follows:

$$D_a = \frac{v_{fs} q d_f}{wV_m} \tag{1}$$

where *v_{fs}* is the fibre volume fraction in the suspension, *q* is the fibre suspension flow rate, *d_f* is the fibre density, *w* is the width of preform, and *V_m* is the moving velocity of the perforated conveyor belt.

For a fibre volume fraction in the suspension of 0.003%, the predicted areal densities of the aligned preforms in test set 1 and 2 were 95.5 and 209 g/m², respectively. Before the resin impregnation, the areal weights of the aligned preforms were measured by a scale with 0.1 mg resolution for a comparison with the calculated values. It was found that the measured values (96, 219 g/m²) agreed with the equation (1) within a 5% error.

Aligned preforms were put onto the epoxy resin film and then heat and compression were applied to enable impregnation to produce prepregs. Subsequently, prepregs were stacked in a semi-closed mould and cured by vacuum bag moulding in an autoclave. At an autoclave pressure of approximately 0.69 MPa, the calculated pressure

Table 2 Specification of composite samples

Areal density of preform (g/m ²)	96	219
Fibre volume fraction (%)	41.4	55
Specimen's dimension <i>l</i> × <i>w</i> × <i>t</i> [mm]	50 × 1 × 0.125	55 × 3 × 0.220
Number of specimens	7	6

Fig. 5. Cross section of aligned discontinuous fibre composite samples.

applied to the 3 mm wide specimens before the mould was closed was 2.15 MPa.

The curing condition was 135°C for 90 min. After curing, the thickness of specimens was measured using a microscope. Based on the areal density, the fibre volume fractions of each specimen were calculated to be 41% and 55% respectively. Specimen dimensions and specification of the aligned short fibre composites are listed in Table 2 and Figure 5 shows the cross section images of the composite samples.

4.3 Mechanical testing

Tensile tests were performed at a test speed of 2 mm/min. A video extensometer (IMETRUM, UK) was used to measure the strain and the load was measured with a 1 kN load cell (Hounsfield, UK) for test set 1, and a 10 kN load cell (Shimadzu, Japan) for test set 2. White dots were painted on the specimens to enable the strain to be measured by tracking the target pixels. The gauge length of the specimens was 5 mm. Glass fibre/epoxy end tabs were attached using an epoxy adhesive (Redux®,

Hexcel) for all the specimens.

5 Tensile Test Results

All of the stress-strain responses for the tensile testing showed straight lines because the carbon fibre length (3 mm) used in this paper was longer than the critical fibre length of the carbon/epoxy composite, typically around 0.5 mm. In this experimental work, thus, ductility or pseudo-ductility was not expected. Fibre breakage occurred first and it led to the complete rupture of the composite.

Figure 6 shows the bar charts with the tensile test results in the fibre alignment direction of test sets 1 and 2 and the reference experimental data as listed in Table 3. The reference set A reported that aligned carbon/epoxy composites manufactured by the conventional wet process using glycerine and a rotating drum had a tensile modulus of 60 GPa and a tensile strength of 650 MPa[6]. In reference set B, specimens were from a short carbon fibre aligned mat manufactured by a modified paper making process and a tensile modulus of 80 GPa and tensile

Fig. 6. (a)Tensile modulus, (b)strength, and (c)strain comparison for 2 sets of developed materials vs. existing experimental data (set A,B and C).

Table 3 Sample specifications in references

	Ref.	Fibre length	Fibre vf (%)	Fibre specification
A	Wong and Turner, SAE, 2009 [11,24]	12 mm	45	Recycled carbon fibres
B	Piggott, CST, 1993 [6]	2 mm	35	AS2 carbon fibres
C	Manufacture's data (Toho)	continuous	60	HTS40 carbon fibres

strength of 425 MPa were observed[11,24]. In comparison with the references, the results for the set 2 were outstanding, showing similar strains to failure as for continuous fibre composites, and tensile modulus and strength of 115 GPa and 1509 MPa, respectively. The test results of this work showed the promising potential of the new fibre alignment method.

6 Conclusion & Future work

In this paper, a new discontinuous fibre alignment method and its development process have been introduced. It showed the potential of the orientation head design for producing tape type preforms. For a feasibility test, a small device was set up and composite samples were successfully produced.

The achievements can be summarised as follows,

1. The new discontinuous fibre alignment method has a unique fibre orientation mechanism: utilising the momentum change of liquid jet when it hits a plate.
2. The new discontinuous fibre alignment method is a continuous and fast manufacturing process because the working liquid is a low viscous-medium (water).
3. The improved orientation head design allows the manufacture of a thin tow type aligned short fibre preform, but also a tape type preform (integrated by multiple tow type aligned preforms).
4. Using the preforms from the new manufacturing method with the 3 mm long carbon fibres, short fibre aligned carbon/epoxy composites with fibre volume fractions of 41% and 55% were manufactured.
5. The high fibre volume fraction of 55% indicates that the composites must have a high fibre alignment.
6. In the fibre alignment direction, the composite with high fibre volume fraction (55%) had a tensile modulus of up to 115 GPa and tensile strength of 1509 MPa.
7. It was shown that with this new short fibre aligned composite, high unidirectional mechanical values – i.e. only slightly less than those of similar continuous fibre composites - could be reached.

In the future, the challenges for this new discontinuous fibre alignment method are to make

composites with 0.5~1 mm long fibres and scale up the device for further studies and mass production.

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